

He sdO stars in the Gaia era

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Table 5.6 Atmospheric parameters for four O subdwarfs.

star	CD-31 ^o 4800	BD+39 ^o 3226	BD+37 ^o 442	BD-3 ^o 2179
T _{eff}	42500	45000	55000	55000
log(g)	5.5	5.5	4.0	4.5
ε _{He}	1.0	1.0	1.0	0.3
log(L/M)	2.4	2.5	4.4	3.9
log(L/d ²)	3.2	3.4	3.8	3.6
d(M=2.0)	0.55	0.49	2.7	1.8
d(M=1.0)	0.39	0.35	1.9	1.3
d(M=0.5)	0.27	0.24	1.4	0.9

note: In this Table, L and M are in solar units, and d is the distance in kpc.

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Table

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CD-31 4800: He sdO star

3.442 v = 6.88
 8560
 4570
 2.85
 0.5A
 2.5A

3.482 v = 6.96
 0.926
 4686
 3.9
 3.6A
 1.1A
 4712

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Figure 5.11 Comparison of observed and computed spectrum for CD-31 4800. (continued)

RV = -280 km s⁻¹

15.5 in → 100 A
 6.45 A/cm

BD+39 3226: ORFEUS II and FOCES

Bluhm et al. (1999)

Spectral classification, high-res.

The first Gaia-based HRD for hot subdwarf stars

sdB stars
sdO stars
sdB+F/G/K
Geier et al. 2018

A sample of bright He-sdO stars

12 He-sdO stars (N- and C subtypes, Schindewolf, 2018)

including CD-31 4800 and BD+39 3226:

- high-resolution spectroscopy:

- Optical/UVA: Keck HIRES, ESO VLT-UVES, ESO FEROS
- FUV: FUSE: 905 to 1185 Å
- UV: IUE, HST-STIS

No RV variations

-Photometry:

- Optical: Gaia, Johnson, Strömgren ...
- IR: 2MASS, UKIDSS
- FIR: WISE
- UV: IUE spectrophotometry

Gaia Astrometry: Galactic Orbits

BD+39 3226

CD-31 4800

Kinematic diagnostic:

U-V Diagram

3 σ contours: Thin disk & Thick disk
(Pauli et al. 2006)

Angular momentum (J_z) vs. eccentricity

CD-31 4800: **Thin Disk**

BD+39 3226: **halo star**

Ne II lines in UVA: CD-31 4800

FUSE: C lines and rotation: [CW83]0904-02

Chemical Composition: CD-31 4800

solar

Chemical Composition: BD+39 3226

1/10 solar

**BD+39 3226 =
1/10 CD-31 4800**

Spectral energy distributions and colours

Spectral analysis: surface gravity g

$$\text{SED Fit: } \theta \propto \sqrt{M/g} \varpi \rightarrow M \propto g\theta^2 / \varpi^2$$

Spectral energy distributions and colours

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Common envelope ejection (CEE)

Formation of sds:

-Strong mass loss close to helium core flash at tip of RGB

(Mengel et al. 1979)

-Common envelope ejection

-Close binaries:

MS/WD companions in close orbits (<math>< 10d</math>)

Double He-WD merger

Zhang & Jeffery (2012)

Binary population synthesis

Han et al. (2003):
2 CEE phases
+ Merger channel
Mass distribution
peaks at $0.46M_{\text{sun}}$

Gravities and Masses of 12 bright He-sdO stars

He-deficient sdB stars

Schneider et al. in prep.

He-deficient sdB stars

Mass Distribution:
mean $0.42 \pm 0.1 M$

Distribution of radii:
mean $0.17 \pm 0.063 R$

Conclusion

- **Quantitative NLTE spectral analysis of the He-sdOs CD-31 4800 and 10 sisters (N & C subtypes):**
BD+39 3226 similar metal abundance pattern but is deficient by a factor of 10

- **Gaia astrometry:**
CD-31 4800 and 8 sisters are disk stars
BD+39 3226 is a halo star

- **Photometry: Gaia+:**
mass distribution consistent with canonical mass, similar to He-deficient sdB stars
BD+39 3226 more massive: $0.8 M_{\text{sun}24}$

